

Investigating the Influence of Transformational Leadership on Firm Performance: Evidence from Selected Industrial Parks in Ethiopia

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of transformational leadership (Transf.Lead.) on firm performance (FirmPR.) in selected industrial parks in Ethiopia. It focuses on four leadership dimensions: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and intellectual stimulation. The study employs both descriptive statistics and structural equation modeling (SEM). It uses an explanatory research approach to analyze data collected from 308 management-level employees across various firms in seven industrial parks. Economic, social, and environmental metrics assess the company's performance. The results indicate that transformative leadership has a strong and statistically significant positive effect on company performance ($\beta = 0.449$, C.R. = 3.549, $p < 0.001$). These findings align with research conducted locally and globally, showing that transformational leadership enhances organizational outcomes, especially in performance-driven industrial settings. The report recommends incorporating transformational leadership behaviors into human resource practices, adjusting leadership strategies to meet triple-bottom-line performance goals, and implementing leadership development programs. The findings provide practical insights for policymakers, the Investment Commission, the Industrial Park Development Corporation, park managers, firms in industrial parks, and organizational development practitioners.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Firm Performance, Industrial Parks, Ethiopia

1. Introduction

Transformational leaders may create an inspiring vision that can drive their followers to take the initiative to complete their tasks and achieve their objectives (Bass, 2000). Avolio, Bass, and Jung (1997) identified four dimensions of transformational leadership. These are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Idealized influence refers to role modeling performance, motivating subordinates to work beyond their self-interest to accomplish common goals through the leader's emotional impact (Avolio & Bass, 2004). Inspirational motivation involves motivating behaviors, which give subordinates' tasks meaning. A leader motivates followers through symbolic actions to commit to the vision of the organization. They promote strong team spirit as a means for leading team members towards achieving desired goals (Avolio & Bass, 2004). Intellectual stimulation refers to the behaviors that inspire subordinates by reframing problems, pushing them to

develop creative and innovative ideas, and by approaching old situations in new ways (Nicholson, 2007). Individualized consideration discusses that the leaders pay individual attention to subordinates' needs and Leader act as a coach or mentor (Nicholson, 2007).

Transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the firm (Shahzad et al., 2022). Leadership roles, individual values and capabilities are fundamental to operational success and firm productivity. Hard values and hard capabilities are critical as they influence productivity more than soft values and soft capabilities (David, 1990). However, leaders should consider soft values, including interpersonal leadership, team, and enterprising capabilities (Cugno et al., 2021). As Pedraja-Rejas et al. (2006) revealed, the positive influence of transformational leadership styles is stronger for small companies than for large companies. Moreover, transformational leadership has been linked to enhanced organizational innovation, which is a critical driver of firm performance.

According to Jensen et al. (2020), transformational leadership positively influences some indicators of firm performance. These scholars confirmed that transformational leadership positively influences firm performance factors, ranging from subordinates' perception of leader effectiveness, leader performance, sales, and profit. While an agile supply chain is seen as a winning option for manufacturing SMEs, a transformational leadership style of the CEO can be a source of competitive advantage to improve their performance (Prabhu & Srivastava, 2023). While transformational leadership is widely recognized for its potential to drive organizational success, the mechanisms through which it influences firm performance, especially in the context of dynamic capabilities and innovation, are not fully understood. This gap in the literature presents an opportunity for a systematic exploration of how these elements interact.

However, the existing empirical studies on transformational leadership and firm performance often treat these constructs. These, a review would provide a more nuanced understanding of the mechanisms at play and identify areas where further empirical research is needed. By addressing these gaps, this study aims to contribute to the development of a more integrated and comprehensive framework that can guide both academic inquiry and practical leadership strategies and support as a background by explanatory research design.

2. Literature and Hypothesis

This part of the literature review is designed to present different research and empirical studies that have investigated the link between transformational leadership and firm performance.

2.1. Transformational leadership

Transformation leadership focuses on addressing fundamental requirements and higher needs while inspiring followers to come up with new-fangled thoughts and make the workplace a better place to work (Ghasabeh et al., 2015). Despite criticism of the application of transformational leadership, Van Knippenberg and Sitkin (2013) categorize the influence of this leadership style into four sub-dimensions (Deinert et al., 2015).

A study by Afsar, Masood, and Umrani (2020) investigated the impact of transformational leadership, including idealized influence, on employee trust and organizational performance in the healthcare sector in Pakistan. Kalshoven, Den Hartog, and De Hoogh (2021) examined the relationship between idealized influence, ethical leadership, and firm reputation in Dutch firms. The study found that leaders who demonstrated idealized influence were more likely to foster ethical behavior among employees, which contributed to an improved firm reputation and better financial performance.

Zhang and Zhou (2019) explored the impact of individualized consideration on innovation in the tech industry in China. The study found that leaders who practiced individualized consideration were more effective in promoting innovation within their teams, which led to improved firm performance, especially in rapidly changing markets.

Nguyen, Mia, Winata, and Chong (2020) examined the relationship between individualized consideration and employee outcomes in the hospitality industry in Vietnam. The findings revealed that individualized consideration significantly improved employee job satisfaction, which in turn led to higher employee retention and improved overall firm performance. A study by Mittal and Dhar (2020) focused on the healthcare sector in India, where individualized consideration was shown to significantly boost organizational commitment

Ismail, Rose, and Chik (2020) examined the impact of intellectual stimulation on innovation and competitive advantage in Malaysian manufacturing firms. The study found that leaders who exhibited high levels of intellectual stimulation significantly enhanced organizational innovation, which in turn contributed to a stronger competitive position in the market. A study by Xu, Zhang, and Liu (2021) focused on the technology sector in China, highlighting the positive relationship between intellectual stimulation and employee creativity. The study found that employees who perceived their leaders as intellectually stimulating were more creative and performed better, contributing to improved firm performance.

According to Nguyen and Luu (2019), findings indicated that Transformational Leadership can foster Organizational Performance through Organizational Learning, Organizational Innovation, and Organizational Culture. Transformational leadership's importance is to empower followers to perform effectively by building their commitment to new values, developing their skills and beliefs, and creating a climate conducive to innovation and creativity (Jannah and Tarmizi, 2021). While some findings (Chen, Sharma, Zhan, & Liu, 2019; Effiyanti et al., 2021; Lasrado & Kassem, 2021) show that CEO transformational leadership has a positive effect on firm performance and organizational excellence, this effect can be negative if firms operate in a changing environment (high technology/low demand uncertainty). Transformational leadership influences organizational performance and culture, with differing effects based on context (Nguyen et al., 2023). Moreover, transformational leaders not only enhance newcomer-supervisor value congruence but also foster organizational change (Mulla & Krishnan, 2022; Bagga et al., 2023).

According to Shahzad et al., (2022), results revealed that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the firm. According to Jensen et al. (2020), transformational leadership positively influences some indicators of firm performance. These scholars confirmed that transformational leadership positively influences firm performance factors, ranging from subordinates' perception of leader effectiveness to leader performance, sales, and profit. While an agile supply chain is seen as a winning option for manufacturing SMEs, a transformational leadership style of the CEO can be a source of competitive advantage to improve their performance (Prabhu & Srivastava, 2023).

2.2. Firm Performance

A study by Lee, Chen, and Hsu (2020) investigated the impact of transformational and transactional leadership on firm performance in the Taiwanese high-tech sector. The study found that transformational leadership, characterized by vision and inspiration, was positively correlated with firm performance, while transactional leadership had a less pronounced effect. Chiu and Lin (2022) add that governance can improve the knowledge-creation process by impacting innovation capability, thereby affecting a firm's performance.

Lee, Chen, and Hsu (2022) explored the relationship between transformational leadership and long-term economic performance in the automotive industry. The study showed that transformational leadership positively impacted strategic decision-making, leading to sustained economic success. Kaur and Singh (2020) examined the influence of transformational leadership on community engagement and social responsibility in the Indian non-profit sector. The study found that transformational leadership significantly enhanced community engagement and the effectiveness of social responsibility programs.

A study by Chen, Zhang, and Zhang (2021) investigated the role of transformational leadership in advancing environmental sustainability practices in Chinese manufacturing firms. The study found that transformational leadership significantly contributed to improved environmental performance by promoting sustainable practices and resource efficiency. Zhang, Liu, and Wei (2022) investigated the relationship between transformational leadership and environmental performance metrics in the manufacturing sector. The study found that transformational leadership positively impacted environmental performance metrics by encouraging practices that reduce carbon footprints and improve energy efficiency. Wang and Xu (2023) examined the role of environmental regulations and shared infrastructure in shaping the environmental performance of firms in industry parks. Their study highlighted the importance of regulatory compliance and technological adoption in achieving sustainable outcomes.

2.3. Hypothesis

This study offered the hypotheses postulate the existence of a relationship among latent variables that construct which is transformational leadership as an exogenous variable, and firm performance as an endogenous variable. Based on the empirical evidence hypotheses were developed below:

2.3.1. Transformational leadership and firm performance

According to Chan et al. (2019), Intellectual Stimulation was the highest level for employees in the manufacturing industry. However, Individual Consideration was the most significant correlation to organization innovation in the manufacturing industry. Johnson and Smith (2020) study found a positive relationship between Inspirational Motivation and various dimensions of firm performance, including customer satisfaction, employee productivity, and financial performance. Martínez et al. (2021) study underscores the role of transformational leadership in promoting innovation and productivity, which are critical drivers of economic success in competitive markets. Xie et al. (2021) study found that leaders exhibiting high levels of Idealized Influence positively impacted firm performance, particularly in terms of innovation outcomes and employee engagement.

Zhang et al. (2022) intellectual Stimulation was found to have a significant positive impact on firm performance, particularly in terms of innovation and adaptability. According to Anwarul et al. (2023), transformational leadership has the highest impact on the organizational performance of manufacturing firms. Under the context of the fourth industrial revolution, the transformational leadership approach has uniquely boosted innovation performance and organizational sustainability simultaneously. Based on the initial assertion, propose the following null hypothesis:

H1a: Transformational leadership has a significant influence on firm performance

According to Kothari, (2003), the conceptual framework shows the relationship between the independent and dependent variable. A conceptual framework for understanding the influence of transformational leadership on firm performance typically involves several key components that help explain the relationship between these two variables.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Developed by researcher (2025)

3. Methodology

A research paradigm refers to a framework or set of beliefs that guide how research is conducted. It encompasses the philosophical assumptions about reality (ontology), the nature of knowledge (epistemology), and the methods used to investigate phenomena (methodology). In addition, the choice of research paradigm significantly influences the design, data collection, and interpretation of research findings and fundamental beliefs and assumptions about the nature of the world (Gioia & Pitre, 1990; Guba and Lincoln, 1994, Mertens, D. M., 2014, Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D., 2018). Positivism is a philosophical paradigm that aligns with the empirical and scientific examination of social phenomena, emphasizing objectivity, measurable variables, and the application of systematic research methods (Park et al., 2020). This study used positivism to investigate the influence of transformational leadership on firm performance in case of selected Industrial parks in Ethiopia. This study used explanatory design with descriptive statistics and structure equation model.

Wang et al. (2019), demonstrates how transformational leadership influence firm performance across various criteria and levels, showing the relevance of examining broader firm contexts. The unit of analysis in this study was firm level and collecting data from management-level employees. This study employed probability sampling of random selection, where every population member has an equal chance of being chosen. This sampling was randomly select respondents from management-level employees in the firms of selected industry, particularly those working in lower, middle- and top-management positions. The total sample size of this study used is 308 out of sample size 325 that calculated by Yamane formula (Yamane, 1967) that determine the sample size.

According to Jos F. Calderon (1993), determining an appropriate sample size depends on factors such as availability of time, cost, human resources, and the nature of homogeneity and heterogeneity of the population from which the sample is drawn. However, in most cases, 10% or more is taken as an appropriate sample size to draw a reliable and representative sample. Several factors influence the sample size decision such as, a minimum number of sample size is needed for data analysis. As a result, SEM is used for data analysis for this study, and the preciseness of the level of measurement is attained if the size is smaller (Hair, et al, 2010).

In addition, Tabanichnick and Fidell (1996) described that a sample size of 300 is considered to be good for essential data in a given population, however, this sample size of 325 for a given population of management-level employees 1,734 was found to provide good data in this study. In this study, the data was collect by using a structured questionnaire, which was consist four sections. Before the full-scale data collection begins, a pilot test was conducted with 10% of the total sample size (Whitehead et al., 2016). Data collection methods in this study was a self-administered survey structured questionnaire that was use a 5-point Likert scale to rate agreement with each statement using a scale of range, depending on the specific questionnaire. The measurement of variables was discussed all latent variables with indicators and descriptions are shown under the table 1 below.

Table 1: summarized measurement of variables

Variables	Indicators	Operational descriptions	Reference's
Transformational leadership (Transf.Lead.)	Idealized influence	Leaders act as role models, demonstrating high ethical standards and gaining followers' trust and respect.	Bernard Bass and Bruce Avolio (2004); Deinert et al., 2015; Montano et al. (2017); Braun et al. (2018);
	Inspirational motivation	Leaders articulate a compelling vision, inspire and motivate followers by providing meaning and challenge.	

	Intellectual stimulation	Leaders encourage creativity, innovation, and critical thinking by challenging assumptions and soliciting new ideas.	Ng and Sears (2018); Kelloway et al. (2021)
	Individualized consideration	Leaders provide personalized support, mentoring, and coaching, recognizing individual needs and fostering development.	
Firm performance (FirmPR.)	Economic performance	Measures productivity, innovations, market share, employment, profitability, revenue growth, return on investment, and cost efficiency.	Morrison & Ziegler (2018); Gordon et al. (2019); Zhang & Zhang (2020); Wang & Wu (2021); Anwarul et al. (2023); Harun et al., 2023; Wang and Xu (2023)
	Social performance	Assesses the impact of the firm on social factors such as employee satisfaction, community engagement, and social equity.	
	Environmental performance	Evaluates the firm's impact on environmental sustainability, including resource usage, waste management, and reduction of carbon footprint.	

Source: Compiled by researcher (2025)

3.1. Reliability and Validity

3.1.1. Reliability Test

According to Hair et al., (2017), reliability refers to the extent to which a variable or set of variables is consistent in what it is intended to measure. If multiple measurements are taken, reliable measures was consistent in their values. It implies that the same thing happens again and over again under the same or extremely similar circumstances.

The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient was used in the reliability analysis of the scales. According to Hair et al., (2017) above, a 0.7 level of Alpha value considered the scale has overall stability and consistency. Cronbach's alpha is a reliability coefficient that indicates how well the items in a set are positively related to one another (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). These, was applied to determine the internal consistency or reliability of the questionnaire.

3.1.2. Validity Test

By establishing trustworthiness, a researcher aims to persuade readers that "the research findings of an inquiry are worth paying attention to" (Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, 1985). Validity is the extent to which a scale or set of measures accurately represents the concept of interest. EFA was conducted to examine the loading of the main research variables. In the beginning, the Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) index and Bartlett's test of sphericity were conducted to ensure that the sample size was sufficient to fulfill the requirement for the EFA, additionally, the KMO and Bartlett's indicate the level of variables dependability. Validation was some evidence on whether the content of the item is relevant in helping to answer the research question and to check the clarity of the question. The process of developing and validating a research instrument is largely focused on reducing errors in the measurement process (Kimberlin & Winterstein, 2008).

Beside, to check the goodness of fit of the model was evaluated using five indices, which reflected the overall model fit: (1) the chi-square statistic; (2) the goodness-of-fit index (GFI); (3) the comparative fit index (CFI); (4) the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) which compared the estimated model with the null model; and (5) the root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA). The GFI, CFI, and TLI usually vary along a 0 to 1 continuum in which values

greater than 0.80 are typically taken to reflect an acceptable and excellent fit to the data (Lomax, 2012). Browne, M. W. & Cudeck, (1993) also suggest that RMSEA less than 0.08 is indicative of a “close fit”.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a tool that is used to confirm or reject the measurement theory and Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a multivariate statistical analysis technique that is used to analyze structural relationships and also SEM combines factor analysis and multiple regression analysis, and it is used to analyze the structural relationship between measured variables and latent constructs (Hair et al., 2017). Therefore, the study was deployed to validate interdependence relationships between each variable; confirmatory factor analysis by using structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed and quantitative data was analysed and discussed through Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) using IBM SPSS Version 25 with AMOS statistical software.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive Analysis on the influence of transformational leadership on firm performance

The descriptive statistics for the Transformational Leadership indicators show that leaders are highly regarded for their capacity to motivate, foster intellectual development, and provide tailored assistance. These results are consistent with a substantial amount of empirical research that emphasizes how important transformational leadership is in influencing organizational outcomes. Higher levels of employee satisfaction, creativity, and performance are frequently linked to leaders who are exceptional at Idealized Influence, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individual Consideration. Studies on the dependent nature of leadership effectiveness, however, support the idea that the effectiveness of these behaviors may vary depending on certain organizational circumstances or individual leader styles, as seen by the fluctuation seen in various indicators (Judge & Piccolo, 2004).

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of transformational leadership dimensions

		Descriptive Statistics	
		Mean	Std. Deviation
Idealized influence	I make others feel good to be around me	3.13	1.281
	Others have complete faith in me	3.60	1.030
	Others are proud to be associated with me	3.63	1.056
	I emphasize the importance of having a collective sense of mission	3.69	1.027
Inspirational motivation	I express with a few simple words what we could and should do	3.96	.966
	I provide appealing images about what we can do	3.85	.949
	I help others find meaning in their work	3.94	.936
	I developed team spirit in employees	3.95	.936
Intellectual stimulation	I enable others to think about old problems in new ways	3.85	1.017
	I provide others with new ways of looking at puzzling things	3.85	.954
	I get others to rethink ideas that they had never questioned before	3.94	.938
	I suggest new innovative ways to complete assignments	3.99	.974

Individual consideration	I spend time teaching and coaching employees	3.52	1.238
	I help others to develop themselves	3.65	.995
	I let others know how I think they are doing	3.69	.995
	I give personal attention to others who seem rejected.	3.95	.997
	Valid N (listwise)	308	

Table 3, the descriptive statistics for the indicators of Transformational Leadership reflect a strong perception of leaders' ability to inspire, stimulate intellectual growth, and offer individualized support. These findings resonate with a large body of empirical literature that underscores the critical role of transformational leadership in shaping organizational outcomes. Leaders who excel in Idealized Influence, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individual Consideration are often associated with higher levels of employee satisfaction, innovation, and performance. However, the variability observed in some indicators suggests that the effectiveness of these behaviors may depend on specific organizational contexts or individual leader styles, as supported by studies on the contingent nature of leadership effectiveness (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Therefore, while transformational leadership behaviors are generally perceived positively, the extent to which they are effective can vary depending on individual perceptions and situational factors.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of firm performance indicators

		Descriptive Statistics	
FPR Indicators	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
Economic Performance	Our firm efficiently used shared infrastructure such as utilities, transportation, and waste management in recent years	3.76	1.103
	Our firm has improved workforce development in recent years	3.60	1.109
	Our firm has improved market conditions, including demand fluctuations and competition in recent years	3.68	1.085
	Our firm has improved adoptions of advanced technologies improved in recent years	3.67	1.162
Social performance	Our firm adhere to labor laws and standards, ensuring fair wages, safe working conditions, and respect for workers' rights improved in recent years	3.50	1.134
	Our firm contribute to local communities through various initiatives, such as local hiring, support for community projects, and partnerships with local organizations has improved in recent years	3.43	1.207
	Our firm build positive relationships with stakeholders, including customers, suppliers, and local communities in recent years	3.56	1.213
	Our firm build trust in ethical behavior, including transparency, integrity, and adherence to anti-corruption standards in recent years	3.54	1.225

Environmental performance	Our firm keep environmental regulations of parks in recent years	3.48	1.084
	Our firm efficiently use shared resources such as waste management, energy supply, and water treatment in recent years	3.49	1.259
	Our firm has improved in terms of adopting advanced technologies for energy efficiency, emissions control, and waste reduction in recent years	3.66	1.111
	Our firm has improved in terms of collaborate to share best practices and environmental management strategies of parks in recent years	3.59	1.201
	Valid N (listwise)	308	

In terms of economic performance, the company has improved in a number of areas, as seen in Table 4 above; the data indicates that the firm has made consistent improvements in economic, social, and environmental performance, with stronger improvements seen in economic and social areas. The higher mean scores in economic and social dimensions reflect effective management and positive societal impact, though the environmental performance, particularly in resource management and regulatory adherence, shows moderate improvement. The variability in perceptions, particularly in environmental and social performance, suggests that while progress has been made, there are still areas where perceptions differ and where further efforts could yield more uniform satisfaction among stakeholders.

In summary, the results of these descriptive statistics align well with empirical studies that highlight the importance of efficient resource use, workforce development, technology adoption, and ethical practices in improving both economic and social outcomes. Moreover, the integration of sustainability into business operations, such as compliance with regulations, efficient resource management, and technological innovation, is essential for enhancing environmental performance and ensuring long-term success in the face of growing environmental challenges.

4.2. SEM Analysis

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) models intricate relationships among multiple independent and dependent variables, accommodating both observed and latent constructs (Jongerling, Lopez-Pernas, Saqr, & Vogelsmeier, 2024). To ensure the validity of SEM analysis, researchers must test several key assumptions, including linearity, normality, independence of error, collinearity diagnosis, and outliers (Kline, 2015). After checking all assumptions developed measurement and structural models.

4.2.1. The Measurement Model of Transformational Leadership Construct

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is a crucial component of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), primarily used to validate the hypothesized relationships between latent and observed variables (Haron, Halim, & Ismail, 2023). This method allows researchers to assess the fit of their measurement models, ensuring that the constructs are accurately represented (Goretzko, Siemund, & Sterner, 2024). This study performed CFA to ensure the factor loadings, validity, and reliability of the scales and constructs used in the study. In the first endeavor of the measurement model, the results did generate a good model fit, while this study has effectively conducted the PCA. According to Hair et al. (2019), PCA helps to evaluate the factor loadings, validity, and reliability of the scales and constructs used in the study. And the components have acceptable factor loadings above 0.50, as shown in the below figure.

As depicted below, the TL construct is made up of 4 latent variables and 12 indicators. In other words, it consists of one second order construct (Transformational Leadership) and four first order constructs; (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized considerations). All the four first order constructs are equally measured through three indicator variables. The items have successfully survived different validity and reliability tests; hence no item is so far deleted because of failing any of those tests including, dimensionality, and alpha score. Thus, the originally adopted 4 latent constructs along with their 12 indicators are going to be tested for confirmatory factor analysis. The following figure (figure 2) illustrates the proposed CFA result for the Transformational Leadership construct.

Figure 2: Higher-order Measurement Model of Transformational Leadership Style Construct
 The standardized estimates from the regression weights provide a crucial understanding of the strength and direction of the relationships between the latent constructs and their respective indicators in the model. In the context of the current study, transformational leadership (Transf.Lead) has significant and substantial relationships with the different dimensions, namely Inspirational motivation (INM), Idealized influence (IDF), Individual consideration (INC), and Intellectual stimulation (INS). Standardized loadings are reported on the arrows connecting latent variables to their indicators, showing the strength of each item in representing the construct. Most loadings are above 0.70, which is considered strong according to Hair et al. (2019), indicating good convergent validity.

In conclusion, the standardized regression weights across all constructs demonstrate strong and statistically significant relationships between latent variables and their respective observed indicators, with all factor loadings exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.50 (Hair et al., 2019). This suggests that the observed variables are good representations of their underlying latent constructs. Overall, the results provide strong evidence of convergent validity and internal consistency, thereby confirming the adequacy of the measurement model for subsequent structural analysis (Byrne, 2016).

Table 5: GOF Statistics for Higher Order Model of Transformational Leadership Construct

Good of Fit Measure	Index	Threshold	Results	Model Fitting Verdict
Chi-Square Fit	χ^2/df or CMIN/df	<3	1.637	Good
Absolut Fit	RMSEA	<0.08	.046	Good
	RMR	<0.08	.043	Good

	GFI	>0.80	.940	Good
Incremental Fit	CFI	>0.90	.975	Good
	TLI	>0.90	.969	Good
	IFI	>0.90	.975	Good
Parsimony-adjusted	PGFI	>0.50	.684	Good

Table 5, describes that the model’s overall goodness of fit was assessed using multiple statistical indices that are commonly recommended in structural equation modeling literature. The Chi-Square to degrees of freedom ratio (CMIN/df) was found to be 1.637, which falls within the acceptable threshold of less than 3.0, indicating a reasonably good model fit (Kline, 2016). This statistic suggests that the discrepancy between the observed and estimated covariance matrices is not substantial, thus supporting the model’s structural validity.

Absolute fit indices also demonstrate strong support for the model. The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) was reported at 0.046, and the Root Mean Square Residual (RMR) was 0.043—both values well below the maximum recommended threshold of 0.08 (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Additionally, the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) reached 0.940, which exceeds the generally accepted minimum value of 0.80 for an acceptable model (Hair et al., 2019). These indices collectively confirm the model’s overall absolute fit to the data.

In terms of incremental fit, the model also performed strongly. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI)-0.975, Incremental Fit Index (IFI)-0.971, and the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) was 0.975. All of these exceed the 0.90 threshold, indicating that the proposed model performs significantly better than a baseline model with no relationships between variables (Byrne, 2016). This provides further evidence that the structural relationships specified in the model are well supported by the data.

Finally, the Parsimony Goodness of Fit Index (PGFI) was 0.684, which is above the suggested cut-off value of 0.50, supporting the model’s adequacy in balancing goodness of fit with simplicity (Mulaik et al., 1989). A model that fits well but also remains parsimonious is considered ideal in SEM, as it avoids overfitting while still capturing the underlying theoretical relationships.

Figure 3: Full First-Order Measurement Model of the Transformational Leadership Construct

The standardized regression weights in the measurement model play a crucial role in understanding how well the observed indicators represent their respective latent constructs. In this case, the standardized regression weights for each indicator were carefully examined to assess the strength of their relationships with the corresponding latent variables. The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) model demonstrates strong measurement quality across the four latent variables—INM, IDF, INC, and INS. Most indicators load highly on their respective constructs, with values generally above .70, reflecting strong convergent validity. INM and IDF show particularly strong factor loadings ranging from .76 to .85 and .81 to .84, respectively, indicating excellent measurement consistency. For INC, the first two indicators load at .69, which is acceptable, while the remaining indicators load strongly above .77. INS displays strong loadings as well, though IS4 shows a lower but still acceptable loading of .61. Overall, all constructs meet the minimum requirements for acceptable factor loadings, and the pattern supports the internal coherence of each dimension.

Table 6: Reliability and Validity Analysis for Transformational Leadership Dimensions

Construct	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	INM	IDF	INC	INS
INM	0.923	0.751	0.390	0.925	0.867			
IDF	0.900	0.693	0.361	0.901	0.601***	0.832		
INC	0.891	0.671	0.525	0.893	0.625***	0.499***	0.819	
INS	0.890	0.668	0.525	0.891	0.611***	0.545***	0.724***	0.817

Note: Diagonal values (bold) represent $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$. Off-diagonals represent construct correlations.
 ***p < .001.

Table 6, presents the key metrics for evaluating the discriminant validity and convergent validity of the measurement model. These metrics include Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Maximum Shared Variance (MSV), and Maximum Reliability (MaxR(H)), along with the correlations between the latent constructs INM, IDF, INC, and INS.

In conclusion, the results from these fit indices demonstrate that the measurement model is robust, with high reliability, good convergent validity, and strong discriminant validity. The CR, AVE, MSV, and MaxR(H) values all fall within acceptable thresholds, confirming that the constructs are measured reliably and distinctively. The significant correlations further indicate the meaningful relationships between the constructs, which strengthens the overall validity of the measurement model in this study.

5.3.2. The Measurement Model of Firm performance Construct

The first construct going to be validated is the Firm performance construct /FirmPR./. This proposed model is composed of higher order construct namely Firm performance and three first order constructs namely economic performance, Social performance and Environmental Performance.

Figure 4: Final higher-order Measurement Model of Firm Performance Construct

The first construct going to be validated is the Firm performance construct /FirmPR./. This proposed model is composed of one second order construct namely Firm performance and three first order constructs namely social performance, economic performance and environmental performance. The measurement model illustrates the multidimensional structure of Firm Performance (FirmPR.), represented by three first-order latent constructs: FRSP, FENP, and FREP. Each of these constructs is assessed through multiple observed indicators, all of which demonstrate strong standardized factor loadings. This indicates that the items reliably capture the underlying dimensions of firm performance. The conceptualization of FirmPR. as a higher-order latent variable is appropriate because firm performance is inherently multidimensional and best reflected through several performance domains.

Overall, the measurement model demonstrates good construct validity, supported by high standardized factor loadings, balanced multidimensional representation, and meaningful contributions of all three performance dimensions to the higher-order construct. The structure aligns with theoretical expectations that firm performance is a composite outcome influenced by financial, external, and internal operational factors. The clear relationships among the constructs demonstrate a well-specified measurement model suitable for subsequent structural analysis.

Table 7: GOF Statistics for Final One Factor Model of Firm Performance Construct

Good of Fit Measure	Index	Threshold	Results	Model Fitting Verdict
Chi-Square Fit	χ^2/df or CMIN/df	<3	2.779	Good
Absolut Fit	RMSEA	<0.08	.076	Good
	RMR	<0.08	.056	Good
	GFI	>0.80	.930	Good
Incremental Fit	CFI	>0.90	.966	Good
	TLI	>0.90	.955	Good
	IFI	>0.90	.966	Good
Parsimony-adjusted	PCFI	>0.50	.746	Good

In evaluating the goodness of fit of the structural equation model (SEM), various fit indices are assessed to determine how well the model represents the data. The results from the analysis show that the model fits the data exceptionally well, meeting or exceeding all commonly accepted thresholds for each key fit index.

The Chi-Square Fit (χ^2/df or CMIN/df) value is 2.779, which is well below the threshold of 3.0 (Byrne, 2010). This indicates a good fit between the model and the observed data, as the Chi-

square statistic is used to test the hypothesis that the model fits the data well. A lower ratio suggests that the model's complexity is justified by its fit to the data.

The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is .076, which is also below the threshold of 0.08, further confirming that the model is a good fit (Browne & Cudeck, 1993). RMSEA measures how well the model fits the population covariance matrix, with values closer to 0 indicating a better fit. A value below 0.08 generally indicates a reasonable fit.

The Residual Mean Square (RMR) is .056, which is below the recommended threshold of 0.08, indicating minimal discrepancy between the predicted and observed covariances (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is .930, exceeding the threshold of 0.80, which suggests that the model accounts for a high proportion of the variance in the data. This measure assesses the proportion of variance explained by the model, and a value above 0.90 is considered excellent. Regarding incremental fit indices, the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is 0.990, which is well above the threshold of 0.90, indicating that the model explains a good portion of the variance in the data compared to a null model. Similarly, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) and Incremental Fit Index (IFI) are .955 and .966, respectively, both of which surpass the recommended threshold of 0.90 (Bentler, 1990; Hu & Bentler, 1999). These indices indicate that the model fits better than the baseline model, and that the model improvement over the null model is substantial.

Finally, the Parsimony-Adjusted Measures, such as the Parsimony Comparative Fit Index (PCFI), have a value of .746, exceeding the threshold of 0.50, indicating that the model fits well while maintaining an appropriate level of simplicity (Bollen, 1989).

Figure 5: Full First-Order Measurement Model of the Firm Performance Construct
 The measurement model depicts three latent constructs—FRSP, FENP, and FREP—each measured by four observed indicators. The factor loadings for all items are high and within the acceptable range, demonstrating strong item reliability and confirming that the indicators effectively represent their intended latent constructs. The presence of distinct error terms for each indicator further shows that the model accounts for unexplained variance, enhancing its measurement precision.

Overall, the model demonstrates strong convergent validity, internal consistency, and an appropriate representation of the multidimensional nature of firm performance. The high factor loadings and theoretically consistent covariances across the constructs reflect a well-specified measurement model that is suitable for further structural equation modeling. These results contribute to the overall model fit, highlighting the importance of using these indicators for reliable measurement in SEM (Kline, 2016).

Table 8: Reliability and Validity Analysis for Firm Performance Constructs

Construct	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	FENP	FRSP	FREP
FENP	0.888	0.664	0.448	0.889	0.815		
FRSP	0.909	0.714	0.471	0.909	0.615***	0.845	
FREP	0.903	0.701	0.471	0.908	0.669***	0.687***	0.837

Note: Diagonal values (bold) represent $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$. Off-diagonals represent construct correlations. *** $p < .001$.

Table 8, shows that the MaxR(H) values, which approximate the upper bound of construct reliability, range from 0.889 to 0.909, closely matching the CR values. This consistency indicates that the constructs are reliably measured and that the latent variables are well represented by their indicators. The close alignment between CR and MaxR(H) further demonstrates the stability and reliability of the constructs.

Overall, the results provide strong evidence of both convergent and discriminant validity. The constructs show high composite reliability, adequate variance extraction, and clear empirical distinctiveness. The correlation values, while significant, remain below the threshold set by the square roots of AVE, ensuring that no construct overlaps excessively with another. This confirms that the measurement model is robust, reliable, and suitable for subsequent structural model analysis.

Figure 6: structural model of the Transformational Leadership and firm performance Construct

The structural equation model illustrates how Transformational Leadership (Trans.Lead) influences a chain of organizational capabilities and firm performance outcomes through multiple latent constructs. Transformational Leadership is measured through four dimensions—IM, IF, IC, and IS—each with strong and reliable item loadings, indicating good construct representation. These leadership dimensions collectively contribute to three mediating innovation capabilities (INM, IDF, INC, and INS), which then feed into Firm Performance through three major outcome constructs: Firm Environmental Performance (FENP), Firm Resource Performance (FRSP), and Firm Efficiency Performance (FREP). The paths from Transformational Leadership to the innovation constructs show substantial positive effects, highlighting that leadership behaviors meaningfully enhance internal innovation processes. In turn, these improved innovation capabilities strongly predict FirmPR (overall firm performance), which then links further to specific performance dimensions such as environmental, resource-based, and efficiency outcomes. FirmAge and FirmSize were included as control variables, though their paths appear weak, suggesting limited influence on the main structural relationships. Overall, the model demonstrates a well-structured and theoretically coherent framework, where transformational leadership drives innovation capabilities, which subsequently lead to improved multidimensional firm performance.

Table 9: GOF Statistics for structural model of relationship between transformational leadership and firm performance

Good of Fit Measure	Index	Threshold	Results	Model Fitting Verdict
Chi-Square Fit	χ^2/df or CMIN/df	<3	1.726	Good
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	<0.08	.049	Good
	RMR	<0.08	.062	Good
	GFI	>0.80	.875	Good
Incremental Fit	CFI	>0.90	.946	Good
	TLI	>0.90	.940	Good
	IFI	>0.90	.947	Good
Parsimony-adjusted	PCFI	>0.50	.855	Good

Table 9, shows that the model fit indices provide strong evidence of a good model fit to the data. The Chi-Square Fit (CMIN/df) ratio is 1.726, which is significantly below the commonly accepted threshold of 3 (Kline, 2016), indicating that the model adequately fits the data. This suggests that the observed and expected covariance matrices are close enough for the model to be considered a good representation of the data.

In terms of absolute fit, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is .049, which is well below the threshold of 0.08 (Hu & Bentler, 1999), confirming that the model fits the data well without suggesting significant misspecifications. The Residual Mean Square Root (RMR) value of .062 is also under the threshold of 0.08, indicating that the residuals are small and suggesting a good fit. Additionally, the Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) is .875, which exceeds the threshold of 0.80, confirming the model’s adequacy in capturing the observed covariance structure (Bentler, 1990).

Regarding incremental fit, the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is .946, which is well above the commonly accepted threshold of 0.90 (Bentler, 1990). This indicates that the model provides a better fit compared to the baseline independence model. Similarly, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) of .940 and the Incremental Fit Index (IFI) of .947 further support the model’s good fit (Tucker & Lewis, 1973). These indices suggest that the model accounts for the variance in the data effectively, making it a robust fit.

Lastly, the Parsimony-Adjusted Comparative Fit Index (PCFI) is .855, which is above the recommended threshold of 0.50 (Marsh, Balla, & Hau, 1996), indicating that the model

maintains a balance between goodness-of-fit and model complexity. This further supports the model's suitability for the data, as it demonstrates a good fit while keeping the number of parameters relatively low. Overall, these fit indices strongly suggest that the model is appropriate and well-suited for the analysis at hand.

5.3.3. Effect Analysis

Table 10, showed the direct effect and by how much the relationship of transformational leadership and firm performance. In addition, the results by how much the control variables (firm age and firm size) affect performance were also presented in the discussion.

Table 10: SEM analysis done to show significant paths (Direct) between transformational leadership and firm performance

Path	Path Coefficient (β)	S.E.	C.R.	P-Value	Decision
FirmPR <--- FirmAge	.029	.582	.561	.561	
FirmPR <--- FirmSize	-.098	.052	-1.883	.060	
FirmPR <--- Trans.Lead	.449	.126	3.549	***	Significant and supported H1a Hypothesis

Note: ***, **, *, ns shows the p-value less than 0.1 %, 1%, 5%, > 5% respectively

The structural model results in Table 10, show that Transformational Leadership has a strong and significant positive effect on Firm Performance ($\beta = .449$, C.R. = 3.549, $p < .001$), providing strong support for Hypothesis H1a. This indicates that firms led by transformational leaders—who inspire, motivate, and stimulate innovation—are more likely to achieve superior performance outcomes. In contrast, FirmAge demonstrates a positive but statistically non-significant effect on performance ($\beta = .029$, $p = .561$), implying that simply being an older firm does not necessarily translate into better performance within this context. Similarly, FirmSize exhibits a negative yet marginally non-significant effect ($\beta = -.098$, $p = .060$), suggesting that larger firms may experience slight performance constraints, though the effect is not strong enough to be conclusive. Overall, these findings highlight that transformational leadership behaviors, rather than structural firm characteristics such as age or size, play a more decisive role in shaping firm performance in this model.

Moreover, the statistical significance of the relationship emphasizes the practical implications for organizations. It suggests that firms seeking to enhance their performance should invest in leadership development programs focused on transformational leadership skills. This may involve training leaders to communicate a compelling vision, inspire employees to go beyond self-interest, and encourage innovative thinking—all of which contribute to improved organizational outcomes (Northouse, 2018). Overall, these results provide empirical evidence supporting the critical role of transformational leadership in influencing firm performance and underscore its value in organizational settings.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

6.3. Conclusion

This study examined how transformational leadership (TLD) affects firm performance (FPR) in selected industrial parks in Ethiopia. Based on Bass and Avolio's (1994) transformational leadership theory, the study measured four leadership dimensions: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and intellectual stimulation. These were viewed as independent variables. The research looked at how these dimensions relate to the economic, social, and environmental aspects of firm performance.

Using an explanatory research design, the study applied descriptive statistics and structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze the data. The results showed a statistically significant and moderately strong positive relationship between transformational leadership and firm performance. The standardized path coefficient (β) was 0.449, the critical ratio (C.R.) was 3.549, and the p-value was less than 0.001. According to Agazu et al. (2025), these findings suggest that transformational leadership practices greatly improve overall firm performance across various dimensions such as economic, social, and environmental performance.

This aligns with previous studies that show how transformational leadership can enhance organizational outcomes. For instance, Javed et al. (2018) found that transformational leadership encourages innovation and team cohesion, which leads to better performance results. Likewise, Ali et al. (2022) studied East African manufacturing firms and confirmed that transformational leaders positively affect employees' psychological empowerment, which boosts firm performance indicators.

In Ethiopia, where industrial parks are becoming increasingly important for national industrialization efforts, effective leadership is essential. Research by Gebremariam & Tefera (2021) highlights the value of leadership practices that foster commitment, motivation, and a shared vision among workers. This is especially critical in industrial settings dealing with challenges like talent retention, productivity, and sustainability.

6.4. Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study and supported by recent research, the following recommendations aim to improve firm performance through effective transformational leadership in selected industrial parks in Ethiopia:

Industrial parks should create structured training programs to build transformational leadership skills among lower, middle, and upper-level managers. The training should emphasize empathy, inspirational communication, vision building, and intellectual stimulation. Yasir et al. (2020) suggest that leadership development is a key investment to enhance innovation and operational efficiency in industrial zones. Recruitment, promotion, and performance review systems should include transformational leadership traits as essential skills. Firms in Ethiopian industrial parks can collaborate with the Ethiopian Investment Commission (EIC), Industrial Park Development Corporation, the Minister of Labor and Skills, Ethiopian Management Institute, TVET agencies, and other international companies to incorporate leadership elements into management certification programs to improve transformational leadership skills.

Leaders must be encouraged to connect organizational strategies with economic, social, and environmental goals. This is particularly important in Ethiopia, where firms are expected to follow sustainable industrialization goals (UNIDO, 2023). Practical steps include setting clear KPIs related to social inclusion, environmental compliance, and innovation. A strong shared vision, a key feature of transformational leadership, should be nurtured at all levels of the organization. This helps align employee goals with firm objectives, improving overall performance. Mengistu and Hailemichael (2020) found that companies with strong cultural alignment reported higher productivity and job satisfaction in Ethiopian manufacturing firms. Transparency and trust can be maintained by establishing regular feedback between managers and staff. Breevaart et al. (2014), shows that transformational leadership significantly boosts performance and employee satisfaction through effective communication and recognition. Creating a work culture that encourages innovation, teamwork, and goal alignment can enhance intellectual stimulation and inspirational motivation. Innovative cultures with transformational leaders tend to thrive in dynamic environments like industrial parks, according to recent studies (Wang et al., 2022).

Finally, this study recommend that ongoing research is necessary to assess the short-term and long-term effects of transformational leadership on firm performance, considering various mediating and moderating factors.

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The data sets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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References:

- Agazu, B. G., Kero, C. A., & Debela, K. L. (2025). Transformational leadership and firm performance: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-025-00476-x>
- Chan, S. W., Ang, S. F., Andleeb, N., Ahmad, M. F., & Zaman, I. (2019). *The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Organization Innovation in Malaysian Manufacturing Industry*. May.
- Dewi Jannah and Latip, A. Tarmizi, T. A. (2021). *A Qualitative Study of Transformational Leadership and Organization Success*. April 2022.
- Effiyanti, E., Lubis, A. R., Sofyan, S., & Syafruddin, S. (2021). The Influence of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Performance: A Case Study in Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(2), 583–593. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no2.0583>
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2017). *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (Issue September)*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05542-8>
- Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage, 438–439.
- M. Anwarul Islam, K., Fakhruzoza Bari, M., Al-Kharusi, S., Bashar Bhuiyan, A., & Faisal-E-Alam, M. (2023). Impact of transformational leadership, human capital, and job satisfaction on organizational performance in the manufacturing industry. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(3), 382–392. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21\(3\).2023.31](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21(3).2023.31)
- Nguyen, N. P., Hang, N. T. T., Hiep, N., & Flynn, O. (2023). Does transformational leadership influence organisational culture and organisational performance: Empirical evidence from an emerging country. *IIMB Management Review*, 35(4), 382–392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2023.10.001>
- Nguyen, T. T. N., & Luu, T. M. N. (2019). Linking transformational leadership and organizational performance: An empirical investigation of manufacturing firms in Vietnam. *Economics and Sociology*, 12(2), 170–191. <https://doi.org/10.14254/2071-789X.2019/12-2/10>
- Prabhu, H. M., & Srivastava, A. K. (2023). CEO Transformational Leadership, Supply Chain Agility and Firm Performance: A TISM Modeling among SMEs. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 24(1), 51–65. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-022-00323-y>
- Shahzad, M. A., Iqbal, T., Jan, N., & Zahid, M. (2022). The Role of Transformational Leadership on Firm Performance: Mediating Effect of Corporate Sustainability and Moderating Effect of Knowledge-Sharing. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13(July), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.883224>